

Growth and Yield Responses of Cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata*) to Different Agriphotovoltaic Growing Conditions

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Abstract

This research provides a comprehensive analysis of the impact of different agriphotovoltaic growing conditions on the growth and yield performance of cabbage. The experiment was laid out in restricted randomized block design consisting of seven treatments with three replications. The treatment of growing cabbage below 3.75 m bifacial photovoltaic panel height with 5.65 m pitch distance showed significantly higher performance compared to other treatments under investigation in growth parameters of cabbage such as plant height (30.37 cm), plant spread (46.27 cm), leaf area (495.33 cm²), chlorophyll content (65.57 SPAD unit). The highest values for yield parameters *i.e* head weight (1.33 kg), head diameter (14.32 cm), yield per plot (31.92 kg), yield per ha (36.94 ton) was recorded in treatment (T₅) where cabbage grown below 3.75 m bifacial photovoltaic panel height with 5.65 m pitch distance. Cabbage grown under treatment (T₅) *i.e* below the 3.75m bifacial PV panel height with 5.65 m pitch distance showed a significantly reduced in time for head initiation (43.47 days) and harvesting (77.53 days). The root parameters like root length (20.87 cm), root fresh weight (42.97 g), root dry weight (13.59 g) was recorded in treatment (T₅). In conclusion, cultivating cabbage below 3.75 m bifacial photovoltaic panel height with 5.65 m pitch distance *i.e* (T₅) proved to be the most effective among all agriphotovoltaic conditions in terms of plant growth and yield parameters.

Keywords: Agriphotovoltaic, Cabbage, Growth parameters, Photovoltaic panel, Yield parameters

Introduction

India is the second-largest cabbage producer globally, following China, contributing 16.55% of the world's cultivated area and 12.79% of the global production. In 2024, Maharashtra grew cabbage on about 130,000 hectares of land,

yielding roughly 247.35 million tonnes in total production. Cabbage is a key vegetable in India, widely grown for both domestic use and export. It thrives in cooler climates, with states like Himachal Pradesh, West Bengal, and Uttar Pradesh being major producers. A staple in

Indian cuisine, cabbage plays an important role in the vegetable economy, despite challenges such as pests and market fluctuations.

Cabbage is commonly consumed in various forms, including salads, boiled dishes, dehydrated preparations, as well as in cooked curries and pickles. It is a good source of essential minerals and vitamins such as A, B₁, B₂, and C. (Hanif *et al.*, 2006). Cabbage is widely recognized for its impressive nutritional benefits, medicinal properties, and therapeutic effects. It is consumed by people of all economic classes across the country, either as a fresh vegetable or eaten raw in salads. Although cabbage is affordable, it is packed with essential vitamins, has a low caloric content, and is exceptionally rich in nutrients.

Rising food and energy demands, particularly in developing countries like India, have made their security a major concern. Agri-voltaic systems address this by using the same land for both solar power generation and farming, with crops grown under and between solar panels based on their specific growth needs.

Agriphotovoltaics is the simultaneous use of the area of land for both Solar Energy and agriculture. The PM-KUSUM scheme promotes the “Solarization” of agriculture. This scheme promotes the setting up of small-scale decentralized grid-connected solar power plants on farmers land. AgriPV are increasingly used around the world due to the multiple benefits. Worldwide various reports which includes from China (Hassanien and Ming, 2017), Spain (Aroca Delgado *et al.*, 2019), Italy (Buttaro *et al.*, 2016), USA (Barron-Gafford *et al.*, 2019), France (Marrou *et al.*, 2013), Germany (Trommsdorff *et al.*, 2021) and India (Malu *et al.*, 2017) have attempted research by integrating APV modules on certain areas of the crop production alongwith energy generation. In India, AgriPV is still under development stage through a few pilots. The use of AgriPV offers many key benefits to a densely populated country like India. The benefits include rural electrification, water conservation, agriculture yield improvement, and sustainable income generation. Presently APV system is a relatively

novel and emerging concept for the country like us, with few studies investigating how crop productivity responds to APV systems. This shall be achieved by gathering evidences and data on agriculture production under an agrivoltaic pilot system as well as quantifying the enhancement in photovoltaic production when co-located with agriculture.

Limited research exists on how different AgriPV growing conditions affect the growth and yield parameters of cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. capitata). This study aims to evaluate the impact of AgriPV environments on cabbage performance and compare the findings with existing research.

Materials and methods

The study was conducted during the Rabi season of 2024–25 at the Agriphotovoltaic Research Project, Manwat, under VNMKV, Parbhani. The field was divided into three agrivoltaic (APV) sections and one open control. The APV setup included zones under panels, between panels, and adjacent open areas. Three types of PV panels (20% efficiency, 11° tilt) were used: bifacial (3.75 m clearance, 5.65 m pitch), monofacial (1.75 m clearance, 7.5 m pitch), and bifacial (1.75 m clearance, 10 m pitch). Healthy 3-week-old cabbage seedlings were transplanted at a spacing of 60 cm × 60 cm on raised beds situated both under photovoltaic panels and in open field conditions. Treatment details consist of planting zucchini in the treatment T₁ – below 1.75 m monofacial photovoltaic panel height with 7.5 m pitch distance, treatment T₂ – in between 1.75 m monofacial photovoltaic panel height with 7.5 m pitch distance, treatment T₃ – below 1.75 m bifacial photovoltaic panel height with 10 m pitch distance, treatment T₄ – in between 1.75 m bifacial photovoltaic panel height with 10 m pitch distance, treatment T₅ – below 3.75 m bifacial photovoltaic panel height with 5.65 m pitch distance, treatment T₆ – in between 3.75 m bifacial photovoltaic panel height with 5.65 m pitch distance and treatment T₇ – control i.e. open field condition. All growth and fruiting parameters were recorded at the time of harvest, while yield and root parameters were recorded after harvest. The data collected

was subjected to statistical analysis of variance as suggested by Panse and Sukhatme (1985).

Results and discussion

Growth parameters of cabbage

The impact of various agriphotovoltaic growing conditions on cabbage growth parameters showed significant variation across treatments, as presented in Table 1. Maximum plant height was observed in treatment (T₅) (30.37 cm) where cabbage grown below 3.75 m bifacial photovoltaic panel height with 5.65 m pitch distance and it was statistically at par with treatment (T₆) (30.20 cm). Whereas, the minimum plant height was observed (25.80) in (T₇) where cabbage grown in open field condition *i.e* control. Maximum plant spread was recorded in treatment (T₅) (46.27 cm) and it was statistically at par with treatment (T₆) (45.73 cm). Whereas, minimum plant spread observed in treatment (T₇) (40.46 cm) *i.e* growing cabbage in open field condition. Highest leaf area was observed in treatment (T₅) (495.33 cm²) and it was significantly at par with treatment (T₆) (493.25 cm²) and (T₁) (491.89 cm²). While, significantly minimum leaf area (479.27 cm²) in treatment (T₇) *i.e* growing cabbage in open field condition. Maximum chlorophyll content was observed in treatment (T₅) (65.57 SPAD) and it was statistically at par with treatment (T₆) (62.20 SPAD) and both were significantly superior over other treatments. While, the minimum chlorophyll content in cabbage was recorded in treatment (T₇) (50.19 SPAD) where cabbage grown in open field condition *i.e* control. Present results are in confirmity with the findings of Potenza *et al.*, (2022) on soybean, Gnayem *et al.*, (2024) on cucumber, Marrou *et al.*, (2013) in lettuce, Min *et al.*, (2022) in kimchi cabbage, Hassanien *et al.*, (2022) in chilli paper.

Fruiting parameters of cabbage

Table 2 depict the effect of varying agriphotovoltaic conditions on fruiting parameters of cabbage. The analysis confirmed a statistically significant influence of the treatments, with pronounced differences

observed among the respective treatments. Minimum days required for head harvest was observed in treatment (T₅) (43.47 days) where cabbage grown below 3.75 m bifacial photovoltaic panel height with 5.65 m pitch distance and it was superior over rest of treatments and it was followed by the treatments (T₆) (45.90 days), (T₁) (47.03 days) and (T₂) (48.10 days). While, significantly the maximum days required in (T₇) treatment (52.20 days) where cabbage grown in open field condition. Minimum days required for head harvest was observed in treatment (T₅) (77.53 days) where cabbage grown below 3.75 m bifacial photovoltaic panel height with 5.65 m pitch distance and it was followed by treatment (T₆) (81.13 days). Those treatments were significantly superior over remaining treatments. While, maximum days required in treatment (T₇) (95.47 days) where cabbage grown in open field condition. Early head initiation under AV could be attributed to reduced abiotic stress, especially during the critical vegetative to reproductive transition phase. Moreover, partial shading might have optimized light distribution across the canopy, supporting more efficient photosynthesis during early growth stages. Present findings were supported by Min *et al.*, (2022) in kimchi cabbage.

Yield parameters of cabbage

Table 3 depict the influence of various agriphotovoltaic conditions on yield parameters of cabbage. The analysis indicates that the treatments had a statistically significant effect, with substantial differences observed among the treatment groups. The maximum head weight was recorded in treatment (T₅) (1.33 kg) where cabbage grown below 3.75 m bifacial photovoltaic panel height with 5.65 m pitch distance. It was statistically at par with the treatment (T₆) (1.24 kg). While, minimum head weight was recorded in treatment (T₇) (1.03 kg) where cabbage grown in open field condition. Maximum head diameter was observed in treatment (T₅) (14.32 cm) and it was statistically at par with treatment (T₆) (13.44 cm) and (T₁) (13.19 cm). While, minimum head diameter was

recorded in treatment (T₇) (11.56 cm) where cabbage grown in open field condition. The results, indicated that maximum yield per plot was recorded in treatment (T₅) (31.92 kg) and it was followed by the treatment (T₆) (29.76 kg). While, significantly minimum yield per plot was observed in treatment (T₇) (24.64 kg) where cabbage grown in open field condition. Maximum yield per ha was observed in treatment (T₅) (36.94 ton) and it was followed by the treatment (T₆) (34.44 ton). While, significantly minimum yield per ha was recorded in treatment (T₇) (28.52 ton) where cabbage grown in open field condition. Under

agriphotovoltaic conditions, cabbage showed superior performance compared to open-field cultivation. Key growth and yield parameters such as head weight, head diameter, yield per plot, and yield per hectare were all higher under the agriphotovoltaic system. This enhancement is likely due to the moderated microclimate provided by the photovoltaic panels, which reduces heat stress and improves water use efficiency ultimately supporting better growth and productivity. Similar results were also reported by Min *et al.*, (2022) in Kimchi cabbage, Tang *et al.*, (2020) in strawberry, Mani *et al.*, (2025) in turmeric.

Table 1. Influence of different agriphotovoltaic growing conditions on growth parameters of cabbage

Treatment number	Treatment details	Plant height (cm)	Plant spread (cm)	Leaf area (cm ²)	Chlorophyll content (SPAD value)
T ₁	Below 1.75 m monofacial PV panel height with 7.5 m pitch distance	28.00	44.86	491.89	56.85
T ₂	In between 1.75 m monofacial PV panel height with 7.5 m pitch distance	27.87	43.49	488.98	54.75
T ₃	Below 1.75 m bifacial PV panel height with 10 m pitch distance	26.93	42.41	483.80	53.11
T ₄	In between 1.75 m bifacial PV panel height with 10 m pitch distance	26.00	41.74	481.55	52.64
T ₅	Below 3.75 m bifacial PV panel height with 5.65 m pitch distance	30.37	46.27	495.33	65.57
T ₆	In between 3.75 m bifacial PV panel height with 5.65 m pitch distance	30.20	45.73	493.25	62.20
T ₇	Open field condition	25.80	40.46	479.27	50.19
S.E m±		0.29	0.44	1.39	1.16
C.D.@5%		0.88	1.37	4.29	3.57

Table 2. Influence of different agriphotovoltaic growing conditions on fruiting parameters of cabbage

Treatment number	Treatment details	Days required for head initiation	Days required for head harvest
T ₁	Below 1.75 m monofacial PV panel height with 7.5 m pitch distance	47.03	84.93
T ₂	In between 1.75 m monofacial PV panel height with 7.5 m pitch distance	48.10	87.27
T ₃	Below 1.75 m bifacial PV panel height with 10 m pitch distance	49.50	89.60
T ₄	In between 1.75 m bifacial PV panel height with 10 m pitch distance	50.07	92.20
T ₅	Below 3.75 m bifacial PV panel height with	43.47	77.53

	5.65 m pitch distance		
T ₆	In between 3.75 m bifacial PV panel height with 5.65 m pitch distance	45.90	81.13
T ₇	Open field condition	52.20	95.47
S.E m±		0.72	1.08
C.D.@5%		2.25	3.35

Table 3. Influence of different agriphotovoltaic growing conditions on yield parameters of cabbage

Treatment number	Treatment details	Head weight (kg)	Head diameter (cm)	Yield per plot (kg)	Yield per ha (ton)
T ₁	Below 1.75 m monofacial PV panel height with 7.5 m pitch distance	1.21	13.19	28.96	33.51
T ₂	In between 1.75 m monofacial PV panel height with 7.5 m pitch distance	1.18	12.30	28.32	32.78
T ₃	Below 1.75 m bifacial PV panel height with 10 m pitch distance	1.15	12.18	27.52	31.85
T ₄	In between 1.75 m bifacial PV panel height with 10 m pitch distance	1.09	11.74	26.16	30.28
T ₅	Below 3.75 m bifacial PV panel height with 5.65 m pitch distance	1.33	14.32	31.92	36.94
T ₆	In between 3.75 m bifacial PV panel height with 5.65 m pitch distance	1.24	13.44	29.76	34.44
T ₇	Open field condition	1.03	11.56	24.64	28.52
S.E m±		0.03	0.64	0.25	0.29
C.D.@5%		0.10	1.98	0.78	0.90

Table 4. Influence of different agriphotovoltaic growing conditions on root parameters of cabbage

Treatment number	Treatment details	Root length (cm)	Fresh weight of root (g)	Dry weight of root (g)
T ₁	Below 1.75 m monofacial PV panel height with 7.5 m pitch distance	18.90	40.17	11.23
T ₂	In between 1.75 m monofacial PV panel height with 7.5 m pitch distance	17.23	38.89	10.69
T ₃	Below 1.75 m bifacial PV panel height with 10 m pitch distance	17.10	36.79	10.34
T ₄	In between 1.75 m bifacial PV panel height with 10 m pitch distance	17.03	35.38	9.76
T ₅	Below 3.75 m bifacial PV panel height with 5.65 m pitch distance	20.87	42.97	13.59
T ₆	In between 3.75 m bifacial PV panel height with 5.65 m pitch distance	19.00	41.10	12.35
T ₇	Open field condition	16.13	33.13	7.88
S.E m±		1.05	1.00	0.77
C.D.@5%		3.23	3.09	2.38

Root parameters of cabbage

The effect of different agriphotovoltaic growing conditions on root parameters of cabbage is

presented in Table 4. Root parameters of cabbage were significantly influenced by the different treatments with marked variation

observed among them. Maximum root length was recorded in treatment (T₅) (20.87 cm) where cabbage grown below 3.75 m bifacial PV panel height with 5.65 m pitch distance and it was statistically at par with the treatment (T₆) (19.00 cm) and (T₁) (18.90 cm). While, minimum root length was found in treatment (T₇) (16.13 cm) where cabbage grown in open field condition. Maximum fresh weight of root was observed in treatment (T₅) (42.97 g) and it was statistically at par with the treatment (T₆) (41.10 g) and treatment (T₁) (40.17 g). While, minimum fresh weight of roots was observed in treatment (T₇) (33.13 g). Maximum dry weight of roots was observed in treatment (T₅) (13.59 g) and it was statistically at par with the treatment (T₆) (12.35 g) and (T₁) (11.23 g). While, significantly minimum dry weight of roots was found in treatment (T₇) (7.88 g). Root length, fresh weight and dry weights were higher under agriphotovoltaic conditions than in open fields, likely due to reduced heat stress and better soil moisture. The improved microclimate under APV promoted healthier root growth and greater biomass accumulation. Similar findings were also reported by Kavga *et al.*, (2017) in lettuce and rocket, Artru *et al.*, (2018) in sugarbeet.

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Conflict of interest

The authors confirm that this research was conducted without any commercial or financial associations that might be seen as a potential conflict of interest.

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